

Characterization of a copper deposit obtained by the electrolytic method

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ABSTRACT

In this work an experimental study of pure copper coatings was conducted. These coatings were carried out by electroplating on mechanical engineering steel parts of grade E335. The study of the influence of different experimental conditions on the rate of recovery allowed us to select the electrolytic bath ($H_2O + Cu_2SO_4$), generator voltage from 0 to 12 V and a current of 0 to 1, 2 A. The electrodeposited layer were characterized by different analysis techniques namely morphology by scanning electron microscopy and optical microscopy. The prepared coatings have, a homogeneous morphology, compact and present a degree of codeposition of particles incorporated in the metal matrix.

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1.INTRODUCTION

Surface treatments carried out by wet process represent today, and for decades, a large part of the market of surface treatments and coating of metallic materials [1].As a result, electrolytic coatings are used in many industrial fields: automotive, aerospace, watchmaking, jewelry, connectors...etc. indeed, Electroplating is a process in which a potential difference is applied to an electrode in contact with an electrolyte resulting in an electronic transfer between the electrode and an ionic species in the electrolyte and the subsequent deposition of atoms of this species on the electrode [2].This technique is relatively simple to implement and it allows to confer to objects functional properties different from those of the solid material. These properties can be aesthetic, anticorrosive or electrical, but also to create various nano structures with specific properties and to coat substrates with complex shapes [3-4].The electrolyte is chosen according to the desired deposit.

The obtained layer has obviously precise characteristics which depend on the different parameters of the

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electrolytic mechanism [5]. To protect the surface of the steel, several protective methods exist, the most important of which are the use of metallic coatings such as zinc, chrome and nickel plating, etc. Copper is widely used in industry because of its remarkable physical and mechanical properties, for example, its electrical and thermal conductivity on the one hand and its resistance to corrosion on the other. In addition, copper is the only naturally colored metal, along with gold [6, 7]. A wide range of electrolytes can be deposited with copper, the main ones being acid sulfate, cyanide, pyrophosphate, and fluoborate. The ductility of copper makes it very favorable as an undercoat in nickel + chrome coatings [8]. The objective of this work is to study the effect of electrolysis time and applied current density on the morphology and electrolytic efficiency of an electrodeposited copper coating on E335 engineering steel. The elaboration technique as well as the influence of these parameters is then carried out using different techniques in order to evaluate the microstructure and the efficiency of the electrolysis.

2- EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES USED

2.1. MATERIALS USED

The substrate used in this study is a steel of grade E335 related to commonly used unalloyed low carbon steel. The content in mass percentage of the elements constituting the substrate, obtained with the help of X-ray fluorescence analysis, is represented in Table 1.

Table 1: Chemical Composition of substrate E335

E335	Fe	C	Cu	Ni	P	Si
	Bal	0,1	0,119	<0,03	0,050	0,044

In our work, we used as anode a commercial copper plate with 99.9% purity (it plays the role of soluble anode) and as cathode a steel E335 (playing the role of substrate). Prior to spraying, the samples are ground and cleaned. The surface to be coated is then degreased and shot-blasted in order to obtain a better adhesion of the enamel.

2.2. THE PROCESS AND THE PROJECTION PARAMETERS

An electrochemical setup was carried out for electrolytic deposition, Fig. (I). The sample of E335 steel (substrate) is taken as cathode, while as anodes we used copper of cylindrical geometry. These electrodes are immersed in an electrolysis bath $H_2O + Cu_2SO_4$, and connected to a current generator that allows us to set the electrical conditions under which the deposits are made (the intensity and voltage).

The two electrodes are arranged in parallel in order to avoid a too great concentration of the current lines at the end of the cathode.

Fig 1: Schematic diagram of an electrolysis cell.

We have carried out the deposits according to different parameters, which are shown in the following table:

Table 2: Projection parameters used

Projection parameters	
Current of the generator	0 à 1,2 A
Voltage of the generator	0 à 12 V
Wire feed speed	0.06 m/s
Solution	H ₂ O+ Cu ₂ SO ₄
Distance	100 mm

2.3. MASS OF THE COATING

The speed of formation of the deposit depends directly on the current density which crosses the cell which is a function of the overvoltage. From the examination of the deposits, we fixed the distance between the two electrodes at 100mm so that we could use a significant variation of the current density. To determine the deposited mass as a function of deposition time and current density, we used Faraday's law. The relation (1) used is then:

$$m = \frac{M \cdot t \cdot I}{N \cdot F} \quad (1)$$

M : the deposited mass, in g

I : current intensity, in A with $I = i \cdot s$

t : electrolysis time

M : the atomic mass,

n : degree of oxidation

F : Faraday constant (96500 Cmol⁻¹)

The deposited mass is equal to the product of the density of the deposit ρ and the volume of the deposit, i.e.

$$m = \rho \cdot v = \rho \cdot s \cdot e \quad (2)$$

With ρ : the density, s : the substrate surface and e : the thickness of the deposit.

2.4 METHODS OF DEPOSIT CHARACTERIZATION

2.4.1. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

The microstructural observations of the Cu deposit were performed by SEM (Japanese brand JEOL JSM-6360LV). Our samples were cut according to recommended dimensions.

2.4.2. OPTICAL MICROSCOPE

The observation of the deposit was carried out using a branded optical microscope (JIOMO) type METAM-P1, with magnifications from 50 to 100. By means of a camera, the microscope is connected to a computer equipped with an image processing software (Matrox Inspector),

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 MEB MICROSTRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

The SEM observations of the Cu deposit elaborated by electrodeposition show a dense, compact and complex microstructure formed by several phases with the presence of porosities and more or less spherical particles (Fig. 2). This microstructure is constituted by lamellae and globular pores and does not present cracks. We also notice that this deposit has a low porosity, this may be associated with the effect of the experimental conditions leading to the formation of the deposit.

Fig 2: Micrograph of the Cu deposit observed with SEM.

3.2 DETERMINATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF PARAMETERS ON THE RECOVERY RATE

3.2.1 THE INFLUENCE OF TIME ON THE RECOVERY RATE

We note that the curve corresponding to the mass obtained as a function of time is relatively increasing. The mass obtained increases by the increase of the time which is very logical and in conformity with the literature. The first part of the curve from (0 to 3 min) the mass is almost constant beyond it increases progressively by the development of time. This implies that time is of great importance on the formation of the deposit.

Figure (3) shows the evolution of the obtained Cu mass as a function of time.

Fig 3: Influence of time on the mass of the Cu deposit

3.2.2 THE INFLUENCE OF VOLTAGE ON THE RECOVERY RATE

Figure (4) shows the mass curves obtained as a function of the generator voltage.

Fig 4 : Influence of the generator voltage on the Cu deposit

From the figure we observe that the deposit mass gain evolves rapidly in a linear way up to a value of 11.8g. Beyond this value it is remarkable to note a stability of the curve which can be explained by the saturation of the solution.

3.2.3 THE INFLUENCE OF THE CURRENT ON THE RECOVERY RATE

Figure (5) shows the evolution of the obtained Cu mass as a function of the generator current.

According to the curve presented on figure (5) we notice that the mass of Cu increases by the increase of the current of the generator to reach a maximum value of 12.6g and thereafter the mass of deposit decreases progressively until stabilizing around a value of 0.7 A. This level of stability can be explained by the saturation of the deposit

Fig 5 : influence of the generator current on the Cu deposit

3.3 OBSERVATION OF THE SURFACE CONDITION OF THE COPPER DEPOSIT AT THE MO

The deposition facies observed by the optical microscope are shown in figure (6).

Fig 6 : Cu deposition facies observed by the optical microscope

Observing figure 6 which represents the micrograph of the copper deposit, we can see that there are two phases the red phase which is the majority which corresponds to the electrodeposited Cu and the black phase corresponds to the coating defect. This micrograph has a red color (color of copper) of rather regular and homogeneous aspect with a weak thickness. We can distinguish heterogeneity of color in the whole surface with the presence of porosities

CONCLUSION

The objective of this work was to broaden the knowledge on, on the one hand, the characteristics of copper coatings (structure and morphology), and on the other hand, the mechanism of development of these coatings. We wondered about the influence of the spraying parameters on the formation of the deposit. A preliminary study allowed us to select the electrolytic bath ($H_2O + Cu_2SO_4$).

- The deposit mass increases, in general, when the experimental duration increases.
- The microstructure of the copper deposits examined by scanning electron microscopy has a homogeneous and compact structure.

- Moreover, it appears that at the chosen processing conditions, a degree of codeposition is obtained. The whole substrate was covered quite homogeneously by solid particles.

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